

Concerted European action on Sustainable Applications of REfractories

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no.101072625

Project Coordinator: **Marc HUGER**, marc.huger@unilim.fr, IRCER

www.cesaref.eu

Deliverable D7.3 - CESAREF Website

Primary author:

Glyn DERRICK

Document contributor:

Marc HUGER

European
Commission

Deliverable D7.3 CESAREF Website

History of Changes for this Deliverable

Version	Date	Author (Organization)	Inputs / Changes
v 0.00	04/01/2023	Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Template
v 1.00	05/01/2023	Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	All pages - Content (first attempt)
v 2.00	06/01/2023	Prof. Marc HUGER - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	All pages - Final Check

Table of contents

- 1 INTRODUCTION..... 2**
- 2 WEBSITE MANAGEMENT 2**
- 3 THE CESAREF WEBSITE 2**
 - 3.1 The Home page..... 2
 - 3.2 The Project page 3
 - 3.3 The Partners page..... 4
 - 3.4 The Team page 6
 - 3.5 The PhD Positions page 7
 - 3.6 The Open Positions page 8
 - 3.7 The PhD Recruitment Procedure page 9
 - 3.8 The PM Recruitment Procedure page 10
 - 3.9 Possible future pages..... 10
- 4 SUMMARY 10**

1 Introduction

The CESAREF Website, dedicated to non-confidential research and network-related communications will target three types of audience: general public without a strong technical background, experts in the field interested in the project results, and participants of the project. This deliverable will present the current status of the website, at the beginning of the project, as well as potential modifications and improvements that could be applied over the course of the project.

The CESAREF website plays a significant role in the dissemination and communication of the project content and activities and describes the current status of the project as well as providing links to the partners webpages. The website aims to introduce the general public to the concept of Industrial Doctorates (ID) supported by Horizon Europe, the PhD students (PhDs) themselves and their research activities. Content presented on the website will be generated through:

- the communication and dissemination activities of the PhDs,
- personal blogs or articles created by the PhDs,
- news and achievements of consortium members,
- news from Horizon Europe and EC websites via “feeds” and
- social media posts.

2 Website management

The website was developed using WordPress and has been operating since April 2022. It is hosted by the Limoges University server and is maintained by a dedicated team (Sebastian Larue, Elsa Thune and Glyn Derrick) to keep it updated regularly.

The website is accessible through the URL www.cesaref.eu.

3 The CESAREF Website

Developed to act as an information hub, about the project’s aims, goals, activities and results, the website will grow and develop over the course of the project lifetime. At this early stage of the project, the website has been focussed primarily on recruiting the highest quality PhD for each of the 15 PhD positions. To achieve this, a series of “Pages” have been created and made publicly accessible. These “Pages” (Home, Project, Partners, Team, PhD Positions, Open Positions, PhD Recruitment Procedure and PM Recruitment Procedure) will be discussed in the following sub-sections.

3.1 The Home page

The CESAREF Home page is designated to familiarize the visitor with the project and provides general information, such as project’s logo, the scope of research, funding, the context of the European Green Deal for the industrial partners and anticipated advances to be made during the project. These points are presented via a collection of written questions and answers, figures and videos as can be seen in **Figure 1**.

Europe goes green thanks to European Green Deal

The European Commission adopted a set of proposals to make the EU's climate, energy, transport and [...]

- What is CESAREF and what is the focus of this network? +
- CESAREF is a MSCA-DN-ID, but what is a MSCA-DN-ID? +
- CESAREF deals with refractory materials, but what are refractory materials? +
- CESAREF will contribute to the European Green Deal, what is the Industrial European context? +

In the European Green Deal context, what are the key topics that will be tackled by CESAREF network? +

News

- Europe goes green thanks to European Green Deal**
The European Commission adopted a set of proposals to make [...]
- You recently got a Master (or PhD) in Materials Science or Engineering? We are still offering 2 PhD (and one PM) Positions**
After the successful bid by the CESAREF consortium, we are now in [...]

HOW STEEL IS CRUCIAL FOR DAILY LIFE OBJECTS?

IMPACT OF THE GREEN DEAL ON STEEL-MAKING?

Figure 1: CESAREF Home page.

3.2 The Project page

The project page, **Figure 2**, describes in more detail the planned activities of the network. A brief overview of the project methodology is presented followed by a description of each of the seven Work Packages (WPs).

Overall methodology

CESAREF's objectives are identified through seven individual Work Packages (WPs). The first four WPs will deal with the scientific objectives coupling experimental, numerical, and environmental aspects like in similar networks of public and private actors. The last three WPs are dedicated to the training and outreach activities, coordination of the network, and dissemination of results.

WHAT IS CURRENT STEEL PRODUCTION ROUTE?

CURRENT DEVELOPMENTS TOWARD GREEN STEEL?

WHAT ARE STEEL PRODUCTION ROUTES CURRENTLY DEVELOPPED USING HYDROGEN?

WHAT ARE REFRACTORY MATERIALS ?

WP 1 - Efficient use of mineral resources and recycling

Efficient use of mineral resources and recycling will deal with the 4 challenges associated with circular economy: feed the loop, design the loop, slow down the loop and close the loop. The Life Cycle Assessment methodology (LCA), which has become a standard environmental evaluation tool (ISO 14040 – 14044:2006), will play a key role in this WP. Feeding the loop in a sustainable way requires knowledge about raw materials extraction (including secondary raw materials) to build robust inventory databases. Designing the loop means having access to relevant production routes of several types of refractories (bricks, precast blocks, unshaped products), to optimize them in an eco-design perspective. Slowing down the loop means the development of refractory products with a longer service life, and closing the loop means the development of refractory products that can be recycled.

Figure 2: CESAREF Project page.

3.3 The Partners page

The 15 Beneficiaries and the 9 Associated partners are presented on the Partner page, **Figure 3**. The full and short names, locations and logos of the partners are displayed, the visitor can also access the partners website by clicking on the logos. The geographical locations of the partners sites are displayed on the map of Europe, the colour code indicates the position of the industrial partner within the refractory supply chain.

15 Beneficiaries

Academics

- irCer** (CNRS) - Institute of Research for Ceramics (IR CER - UMR CNRS 7315) - Limoges (France)
- PIMM** (CNRS) - Processes and Engineering in Mechanics and Materials (PIMM - UMR CNRS 8006) - Paris (France)
- CHEMENG** (ULIEGE) - Department Chemical Engineering (CHEMENG) - University of Liege (ULIEGE) - Liège (Belgium)
- GEMME** (ULIEGE) - Department Minerals Engineering, Materials & Environment (GEMME) - University of Liege (ULIEGE) - Liège (Belgium)
- MONTAN** (TUWIEN) - Chair of Ceramics - Montan Universität Leoben (CoC - MUL) - Leoben (Austria)
- RWTH AACHEN** (RWTH) - Institute of Mineral Engineering, Chair of Ceramics (Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule (RWTH) Aachen (Germany)
- IET** (TUWIEN) - Institute of Energy Systems and Thermodynamics (IET) - Technische Universität Wien (TUWien) - Wien (Austria)
- BAM** - Division 8.5 Micro Non-Destructive Testing - Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM) - Berlin (Germany)

Industrials

- Elkem** - Elkem Silicon Product Development (ELKEM) - Kristiansand (Norway)
- IMERYS** - IMERYS - Vaux Milleu (France)
- calderys** - Division High Temperature Solutions (CALDERYS) - Neuwied (Germany)
- RHI MAGNESITA** - Technology Center Leoben (RHI Magnesita) - Leoben (Austria)
- VESUVIUS** - Refractories Research Centre (VESUVIUS) - Ghlin (Belgium)
- SAINT-GOBAIN** - Performance Ceramics and Refractories (St-Gobain Research Provence) - Cavallon (France)
- TATA STEEL** - Ceramics Research Centre (TATASTEEL) - IJmuiden (Netherlands)
- ArceLorMittal** - Research and Development Campus (ARCELORMITTAL) - Maizières-les-Metz (France)
- SAFRAN** - Department Research and Development (Safran Tech) - Colombes (France)

10 Associated Partners (Academics/Industries)

- Université de Limoges** - Doctoral School n°431 - Sciences et Ingénierie des Matériaux, Mécatronique, Énergétique - (SRMME) - University of Limoges (UNILIM) - Limoges (France)
- Arts et Métiers** - Doctoral School n°432 - Sciences des Matières de l'Ingénieur - (SMI) - Arts et Métiers - Paris (France)
- DFPT** - Institute of Physics and Astronomy - University of Potsdam (DFPT) - Potsdam (Germany)
- fire** - Federation for International Refractory Research and Education (FIRE) - IJmuiden (Netherlands)
- HOCHSCHULE KOBLENZ** - Department Materials Engineering Glass & Ceramics - Koblenz University of Applied Science (HSK) - Koblenz (Germany)
- ALMATIS** - Department Research and Development - Almatix Premium Almatix - Frankfurt (Germany)
- Pyrotek** - ISOMAG Division - Pyrotek Scandinavia AB - Ed (Sweden)
- REFRATECHNIK** - Research and Development - Refraktech Aika Group (216) - Rajshchinsk Aika - Hongkong
- STEULER** - Department Development and Application Technology Refractory Linings - Steuler - Hildersheim (Germany)
- Seoul National University** - Department of Materials Science and Engineering - Seoul National University - Seoul (South Korea)

Figure 3: CESAREF Partner page.

3.4 The Team page

The Team page, **Figure 4**, introduces the visitors to the Management Team, Recruitment, Training and Skill Progress Committee (RTSPC) and the local management team for each PhD position. For each position the photo, name, position, contact information and online profile are available. The corresponding information relating to the PhDs, as well as introductory videos, will most likely be included here in the near future.

The screenshot shows the CESAREF website's 'Team' page. At the top, there are logos for ESAREF, CESAREF (Concerted European action on Sustainable Applications of REfractories), Doctoral Network, and the European Commission. A navigation menu includes Home, Project, Partners, Team, PhD Positions, Open Positions, PhD Recruitment Procedure, and PM Recruitment Procedure.

Management team

- Prof. Marc HUGER**: Cesaref Coordinator, marc.huger@unilim.fr, [LinkedIn](#)
- Séverine ROMERO BAIVIER**: Deputy Coordinator, severine.romero.baivier@yesuvius.com, [LinkedIn](#)
- To be recruited**: Project Manager, [To be defined](#), [LinkedIn](#)

Recruitment, Training and Skill Progress Committee (RTSPC) chaired by:

- Simon ETZOLD**: Co-Chairing RTSPC, etzold@ghi.rwth-aachen.de, [LinkedIn](#)
- Dr. Elsa THUNE**: Co-Chairing RTSPC, elsa.thune@unilim.fr, [LinkedIn](#)

PhD 01 : Documenting the upstream of refractories manufacturing

Academic Supervision (GEMME, University of Liege, Belgium)

- Prof. Eric PIRARD**: Full Professor, eric.pirard@uliege.be, [LinkedIn](#)
- Dr. Hassan BOUZAHZAH**: Senior researcher GeMMe, hassen.bouzahzah@uliege.be, [LinkedIn](#)

Industrial Supervision (RHI Magnesita, Leoben, Austria)

- Dr. Daniela GAVAGNIN**: Head of Pioneer Research, daniela.gavagnin@RHIMagnesita.com, [LinkedIn](#)
- Dr. Thomas DRNEK**: Head of the depart. for Environment and Energy, thomas.drnek@RHIMagnesita.com, [LinkedIn](#)

Figure 4: CESAREF Team page.

3.5 The PhD Positions page

The PhD Positions page, **Figure 5**, indicates the proposed title and a brief summary of each of the 15 PhD projects available. If the visitor is interested in more detailed information on any of the projects, a one-page flyer has been prepared and can be downloaded from this page. The proposed start dates and links to the supervising partners websites are also included.

The screenshot shows the CESAREF website's PhD Positions page. At the top, there are logos for CESAREF, the Doctoral Network, and the European Commission. A navigation menu includes links for Home, Project, Partners, Team, PhD Positions (highlighted), Open Positions, PhD Recruitment Procedure, and PM Recruitment Procedure. The main heading reads: "15 PhD positions on multi-scale refractory materials research, with a circular economy approach". Below this, it states: "A brief description of each PhD can be found below". A highlighted text block says: "You recently got a Master in Material Science or Engineering, and you are looking for a PhD Position, we are still searching for 2 of the brightest young minds. Have a look on PhD 08 and PhD 13." Further down, there are instructions: "Click on the links for more detail about the research and locations for open positions (PhD 08 and PhD13). Please contact the [local supervisory teams](#) for more information. For application, go to the [procedure recruitment page](#)." A specific PhD position is listed: "PhD 01 - Documenting the upstream of refractories manufacturing". The description for PhD 01 states: "This PhD thesis will significantly improve LCA of refractory products by compiling a unique anonymized database of worldwide refractory raw materials. The project will also consider the use of indicators to promote sustainable production processes from cradle to gate. The PhD project will contribute to a better definition of resource depletion by taking into account the transfer of materials from the geosphere to the anthroposphere and the fate of refractory materials at end-of-life (dissipation, recycling, abandon, etc.). A 36 Months PhD starting in October 2022 and supervised between [GEMME-Liege \(Belgium\)](#) and [RHIM-Leoben \(Austria\)](#)". A note below says: "MORE INFORMATION about this Specific PhD 01 Position (application closed)". On the right side, there is a video player titled "ABOUT DOING A PHD WITHIN MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS" with a thumbnail showing a person in a lab.

Figure 5: CESAREF PhD Positions page.

3.6 The Open Positions page

The Open Positions page, **Figure 6**, displays any open positions in the network. Brief descriptions of the available posts along with links to more detailed information and application procedures are located here. As the positions are filled, the corresponding posts are removed. This page will be closed when the recruitment is complete.

Home Project Partners Team PhD Positions **Open Positions** PhD Recruitment Procedure PM Recruitment Procedure

A SECOND RECRUITMENT CAMPAIGN IS NOW OPEN FOR 2 PhD POSITIONS (PhD 08 and PhD 13) and ONE PROJECT MANAGER POSITION (PM)
A brief description of each Position can be found below

You recently got a Master in Material Science or Engineering, and you are looking for a PhD Position, we are still searching for 2 of the brightest young minds. Have a look on PhD 08 and PhD 13

You recently got a PhD in Material Science or Engineering, and you are looking for a Project Manager Position, we are still searching for a well organised young mind. Have a look on PM

PM (Project Manager) - Assist the General Coordinator in the management of CESAREF project
Managing the day-to-day operational aspects. Ensuring proper communication between the 15 beneficiaries and 10 associated partners and with the different boards, the EU Project Officer and CNRS administrative departments. Having a clear picture of deliverables and timelines. Ensuring coordination among all partners. Ensuring completion of project documentation. Assisting partners for administrative implementation. Keeping track of the budget of 4.1 M€. Organizing project meetings, trainings sessions, and secondments for 15 PhD students and all related events (lectures, facility visits, e-trainings etc.). Following-up exploitation, dissemination and open science actions. Implementing communication actions (newsletter writing, project's website update, interviews, public engagement etc.). Preparing (when necessary) amendments to the grant agreement.
A 48 Months PM Contract starting in October 2022 and supervised between [IRCCER-Limoges \(France\)](#).
[MORE INFORMATION about this Specific PM Position?](#)
[HOW TO APPLY for this Specific PM Position?](#)

PhD 08 - Discrete Element Method to support microstructure design of refractories
To conduct developments of numerical tools based on the discrete element method (DEM) for investigation of the relationships between microstructure and thermomechanical properties of model materials. These developments include debonding, thermomechanical coupling, crack-closure and anisotropic behaviours. These developments will lead to a "virtual numerical lab" able to provide tensile, dilatometry, fracture mechanics or thermal shock virtual tests for virtual characterizations. The related developments will be integrated to the free DEM software GranOO.
A 36 Months PhD starting in October 2022 and supervised between [IRCCER-Limoges \(France\)](#) and [IMERYS-Vaux-le-Milieu \(France\)](#).
[MORE INFORMATION about this Specific PhD 08 Position?](#)
[HOW TO APPLY for this Specific PhD 08 Position?](#)

PhD 13 - Performance prediction and reusability/recyclability assessment of refractory materials using online sensing, machine learning and digital decision-making tools

ABOUT DOING A PHD WITHIN MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS
Marie Skłodowska-Curie acti...
YouTube

AS A PHD APPLICANT IN 2022, WHAT CAN YOU LEARN FROM FORMER PHD STUDENTS INVOLVED WITH SISTER PROJECT ATHOR (2017-2022)?
> What can you learn from Diana?
ESR1 -Diana Vitiello
Diana VITIELLO was the PhD1 within ATHOR ([www.athor.../diana-vitiello](#))
YouTube

Figure 6: CESAREF Open Positions page.

3.7 The PhD Recruitment Procedure page

Two recruitment campaigns for the 15 PhD students were launched for the CESAREF project, the details regarding the recruitment process, admissibility of candidates, application materials, contracts, salaries and benefits are presented on this page, **Figure 7**. When the recruitment stage of the project has come to an end, this page will be closed.

We are still looking for 2 PhD students (for PhD 08 and PhD 13) to join our project to participate in multi-scale refractory materials research, with a circular economy approach

Recruitment process

A 1st recruitment campaign took place from April, 27th to July, 29th, and is now closed.
A second recruitment campaign took place from July, 29th to October, 29th, for the PhD 08 and PhD 13 and is now closed.

The recruitment campaigns of the 15 PhD students is now closed.

Admissibility Requirements

Applicants need to fulfill eligibility criteria

- Supported researchers must be doctoral candidates, i.e. not already in possession of a doctoral degree at the date of the recruitment. Researchers who have successfully defended their doctoral thesis but who have not yet formally been awarded the doctoral degree will not be considered eligible.
- Conditions of international mobility of researchers: researchers must undertake trans-national mobility (i.e., move from one country to another) when taking up the first appointment (first recruitment period within CESAREF project). At the time of selection by the host organization, researchers must not have lived or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in the country of their host organization for more than 12 months in the 3 years immediately prior to their recruitment. Short stays, such as holidays, are not considered.

For example, if you apply for a PhD between Norway and France, starting in Norway for 9 months and continuing in France, you should not have spent during the last 3 years more than 12 months in Norway, but there is no limitation related with your previous stays in France.

For further information regarding the eligibility criteria, please refer to the [official documents](#) of the funding agency (pp. 79-80).

Application materials

Candidates send the following documents (provided in English language and combined into a single pdf file) to the Recruitment, Training and Skill Progress Committee (RTSPC) of CESAREF: cesaref.rtspc@unilim.fr

The Recruitment, Training and Skill Progress Committee (RTSPC) establishes well-defined recruitment criteria to be used by all partners and ensure fairness of selection, in accordance with the [Charter & Code for researchers](#). Therefore, the pre and final selection is made in a collective, open, transparent, and merit-based process, led by the RTSPC.

- [CESAREF PhD Application Form](#) to be filled
- Curriculum Vitae: a professional-scientific CV should contain your name (in capital letters), your first name (in small letters), a photo, your birthdate or your age, the main academic degrees you got with date of diplomas obtention and grades, the different personal experiences (internships and jobs) that could demonstrate that your current skills could be in line with the CESAREF PhD topics for which you would like to apply; ideal CV format is [European format](#).
- Cover letter, indicating the selected project(s) and the motivation for your choice. Discuss your skills adapted to the selected topic. When possible, to support your arguments, indicate reference persons (Name / Institution / Email) who could agree to recommend you during the CESAREF recruitment process.
- Copy of your ID card or other form of identification.
- Certificate of master's degree (or equivalent) with transcripts of records
- Summary of the master's degree thesis
- Work experience certificates, if applicable
- Proof of English proficiency, if possible

All official certificates should be provided in their original European language or with an associated official English translation for non-European documents.

In case of open questions, please contact the main supervisor of the PhD position that you are applying for.

Contract, salary and benefits

The successful candidates will receive an attractive salary in accordance with the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions (MSCA) regulations for PhD students. The exact salary will be confirmed upon appointment and is dependent on the [country correction factor](#) (to allow for the difference in cost of living in different EU Member States). The pay includes a living allowance (€800/month), a mobility allowance (€600/month) and a family* allowance (if married or with children; €660/month). Taxation and social (including pension) contribution deductions based on national and company regulations will apply.

*Family = be married / be in a relationship with equivalent status to a marriage recognized by the legislation of the country or region where it was formalized/have dependent children who are being supported by the researcher.

CESAREF being a network of Industrial Doctorates, each PhD student will be recruited 18 months first by the Industrial and then 18 months by the academic in charge of its co-supervision. Researchers are employed on fixed-term contracts and are registered as staff candidates for PhD degrees. They are entitled to pension contributions, paid holidays, and other employment benefits as governed by the universities and industrial companies.

In addition to their individual scientific projects, all PhDs will benefit from further continuing education, which includes a variety of training modules (interactive and international) as well as transferable skills courses and active participation in workshops and conferences. To prepare young researchers for their future careers, a Personal Career Development Plan (PCDP) will be developed together with the RTSPC, the PhD-Ed and the PhD student.

MORE INFORMATION ABOUT THE HORIZON EUROPE FRAMEWORK RESEARCH PROGRAM, MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS AND DOCTORAL NETWORKS

> The European Research Area (ERA)

> Horizon Europe – the new EU research and innovation programme (2021-2027)

> Horizon Europe: Investing in our future together

> The Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions: 20 years of supporting researchers

Figure 7: CESAREF PhD Recruitment Procedure page.

3.8 The PM Recruitment Procedure page

The application materials, contracts, salaries and benefits regarding the recruitment of a project manager are located on this page, **Figure 8**. When the recruitment stage of the project has come to an end, this page will be closed.

We are now also looking for a Project Manager to join our consortium and in order to manage the overall actions involved within this coming European Project CESAREF (Starting in October 2022)

Recruitment process

The recruitment campaign for the project manager took place from July, 25th to October, 25th, and is now closed.

Application materials

Candidates send the following documents (provided in **English language** and combined into a **single pdf file**)

to the Recruitment, Training and Skill Progress Committee (RTSPC) of CESAREF: cesaref_rtspc@unilim.fr

The Recruitment, Training and Skill Progress Committee (RTSPC) establishes well-defined recruitment criteria to be used by all partners and ensures fairness of selection, in accordance with the [Charter & Code for researchers](#). Therefore, the pre and final selection is made in a collective, open, transparent, and merit-based process, led by the RTSPC.

- CESAREF PM Application Form to be filled
- Curriculum Vitae: a professional-scientific CV should contain your name (in capital letters), your first name (in small letters), a photo, your birthdate and your age, the main academic degrees you got with date of diploma obtention and grades, the different personal experiences (internships and jobs) that could demonstrate that your current skills could be in line with the CESAREF Project Manager position for which you would like to apply: Ideal CV format is [European format](#).
- Cover letter, indicating your motivation for this Project Manager position. Discuss your skills adapted to this Project Manager tasks. When possible, to support your arguments, indicate reference persons (Name / Institution / Email) who could agree to recommend you during the CESAREF recruitment process.
- Copy of your ID card or other form of identification
- Certificate of master's and PhD's degrees (or equivalent) with transcripts of records
 - Summary of the master's degree thesis and of the PhD's degree thesis
 - Work experience certificates, if applicable
 - Proof of English proficiency, if possible

All official certificates should be provided in their original European language or with an associated official English translation for non-European documents.

In case of open questions, please contact Marc HUGER (as General Coordinator of this CESAREF European project).

Contract, salary and benefits

The successful candidate will receive an attractive salary in accordance with a CNRS Research Engineer Grade with experience and qualifications. This is thus a quite interesting opportunity to join this prestigious international research institution (CNRS).

DESAREF being an European Project starting in October 2022 and ending in september 2026, the Project Manager will be recruited for 4 years (starting as soon as possible). The Project Manager will be employed by French CNRS on a fixed-term contract and will be registered as staff of IRCER CNRS Laboratory in Limoges. The Project Manager is entitled to pension contributions, paid holidays, and other employment benefits as governed by the French CNRS.

In addition to previous points, the Project Manager will benefit from high-quality work & life environment at IRCER CNRS Laboratory in Limoges with possibilities of partial home office.

MORE INFORMATION ABOUT THE HORIZON EUROPE FRAMEWORK RESEARCH PROGRAM, MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS AND DOCTORAL NETWORKS

> The European Research Area (ERA)

> Horizon Europe – the new EU research and innovation programme (2021-2027)

> Horizon Europe: Investing in our future together

Figure 8: CESAREF PM Recruitment Procedure page.

3.9 Possible future pages

As the project evolves, the website will inevitably change with it, recruitment-based pages will be closed and pages dedicated to content generated by the consortium will be created. Possible topics to be covered by future pages could include:

- Outreach activities
- Public documentation
- Academic publications
- Training events organised by CESAREF
- Involvement of CESAREF at international conferences

4 Summary

The CESAREF website is an online tool to communicate the results and events in the framework of the project. It will be regularly updated and improved by project members (project manager and PhDs) in order to provide the latest news, relevant results and breakthroughs. It will remain available for 3 years after the end of the project. The simplicity of navigation and design allows easy access to information and to contact details for the project's representatives.